

InvenioRDM integration for the CERN Digital Memory platform.

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The CERN Digital Memory project is building a platform to enable long-term preservation of data from a number of different sources of digital repositories and sources. We are currently able to harvest data, package it in a consistent way and process it validating metadata, calculating checksums and running some long-term preservation processes on them. InvenioRDM is a software developed at CERN allowing to create research data management (RDM) repositories. In order to keep developing the platform, I have been working on the deployment of an InvenioRDM instance and its integration with the Digital Memory platform to allow archived records and resources to be accessed, indexed and searched on a public-facing repository powered by InvenioRDM.

ABSTRACT

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During my stay at CERN, I developed a new functionality in the CERN Digital Memory Platform to allow users to create and export their files through the integration of a public repository developed at CERN: InvenioRDM. Therefore, users using the platform will have the possibility to upload the metadata of their files to the public repository. In this way, they will have the opportunity to have all the information of their files centralized in a public repository accessible to the entire CERN community.

To develop the functionality I had to implement a Restful API to integrate the CERN Digital Memory Platform with InvenioRDM. Another important task I tackled was the versioning system of the Digital Memory Platform against the InvenioRDM repository.

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1 INTRODUCTION

CERN is home to the world's largest physics laboratory. This fact can be illustrated in many ways. However, one of the most impressive is the amount of significant data produced: more than 30 petabytes of data per year from the LHC experiment, not counting articles, reports and various papers produced by CERN researchers and staff. [6].

These data may be of great relevance as they are unique, with the potential to harbor great discoveries that have not yet been unveiled. Moreover, they will not only be used by thousands of people around the world to conduct their research soon, but also in future decades to conduct research, track data, and reproduce it. Therefore, all of this data must be preserved while facing the challenges presented by continuous technological improvements and changes: File formats (and encodings) that are no longer supported as better ones become available, migration to new platforms, Operative Systems and frameworks, DevOps approaches are changing how software is deployed and datasets generated, making some of them obsolete, etc.

Because of this need, CERN decided to create a data preservation strategy to efficiently store and access this data, preserving its integrity for future access. Not only is it necessary to preserve the data obtained directly from experiments, but also the work generated as a result of this data, such as researchers' notes and papers, events taking place at CERN, code and software generated. And to meet this need, the CERN Digital Memory Platform was born. The main goal of the CERN Digital Memory Platform is to enable long-term data preservation strategies for several different repositories and digital sources. It will therefore provide digital archiving services to all people working at CERN, allowing to preserve the digital assets produced during their working years.

During my time at CERN, I developed a new functionality in the CERN Digital Memory Platform enabling users to create and export their archives through the integration of a public repository developed at CERN: InvenioRDM.

This report presents the development of the aforementioned functionality. For a better understanding of the document, I will introduce the key concepts as well as the motivation for implementing this new functionality. Technical explanations and detailed descriptions of the implementation will also be given. Finally, an overview of possible future developments and improvements will be described.

Keywords: Digital Cern Memory Platform, InvenioRDM, integration, OAIS Reference Model, step, model, version.

2 BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE AND DEFINITIONS

2.1 Background knowledge

For a better understanding of the technical information related to the project, here I introduce the basic knowledge related to the different technologies and platforms that will be presented throughout the report.

2.1.1 OAIS Reference Model

The Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model defines standards and best practices for long-term digital data preservation system without specifying an implementation.

The OAIS Reference Model is best illustrated by a basic flow diagram of the model's functional entities and the relationships between them.

Figure 1: OAIS Functional Entities [16]

In figure 1, we can observe the six main functional entities and their interfaces in the OAIS model. The lines connecting the entities identify the communication paths through which the information flows.

The flow starts when the producer (person, system or entity) provides data, that needs to be preserved and archived, to the system. The producer submits a Submission Information Package (SIP) that has to be accepted by the **Ingest Functional Entity functions**. Every SIP must provide the content information that is composed of the Content Data Object and its Representation Information (*for more information visit the official project repository [3]*). The Ingest Entity is responsible for: performing quality assurance on the Submission Information Packages, generating an Archival Information Package (AIP) and coordinating updates to the main Storage system. The AIP is formed by one or more Archival Information Unit (AIU, represents the artifact of a record, which it is the "product" produced during the runtime) and an Archival Information Collection (AIC, contains the metadata)

After the SIP has been accepted and processed by the Ingest Functional Entity, the **Archival Storage Functional Entity** has to provide the services and functions for the maintenance and management of the AIP produced in the previous stage. It includes receiving the AIPs, incorporating them into the permanent storage system, and maintaining them by performing error checks and providing recovery capabilities.

At the same time, the **Data Management Functional Entity** provides the services to populate, access and maintain the data used to manage the archive and the one that identifies the documents.

The **Administration Functional Entity**, which is involved in all stages of the data flow, provides the services for the overall operation of the Archive system. This includes requesting submission agreements, auditing submissions, and managing the configuration of all infrastructure, software, and hardware.

The **Preservation Planning Functional Entity**, which is also involved in all stages of the Archive system, is responsible for monitoring the OAIS environment, providing preservation recommendations and plans to ensure that all data in the archive is accessible for the long term.

Finally, the entity responsible for providing services and functions that help consumers locate and check the availability of resources stored in the OAIS is the **Access Functional Entity**. Access functions include communicating with consumers to receive requests and enforcing access limits depending user privileges and system policies.

- CERN’s model for the archival system

As mentioned above, the OAIS model does not specify any implementation. Consequently, the CERN Digital Memory Platform team has had to design an implementation following the recommendations and guidance provided by the OAIS model, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CERN Adaptation of the OAIS model for the Digital Memory Platform [14]

2.1.2 Digital CERN Memory Platform

Based on the OAIS model, the CERN Digital Memory team decided to develop its own implementation of the model to create the organization’s digital platform for data preservation: **The CERN Digital Memory Platform**. The reason for following the OAIS model is to provide a level of trust for CERN’s digital repositories. Therefore, the Digital Memory Platform must be based on these accepted standards and practices.

The key to the design of any digital preservation system is that the information it contains must remain accessible for a long period of time. It is well known that no hardware or software manufacturer can be expected to design a system for eternal preservation. Hence the need to create a digital preservation platform that provides for hardware or software failure and obsolescence. [13]

The CERN Digital Memory Platform is CERN’s project to preserve, digitize and index all CERN multimedia material developed at CERN. The main objective is to provide a digital archiving service

that CERN collaborators can use to preserve, in digital format, their assets in a long-term preservation repository. In the case of resources produced by legacy systems, to save them from deterioration and create open access to a wide audience by uploading them to CERN's institutional repositories. On the other hand, already digital native resources must be preserved for future access, regardless of format or technology. In addition, all data produced internally by CERN users, such as CodiMD notes and Indico events, should be preserved, as they may contain information relevant to the future of the organization.

- **Main Functions:** As stated in the master's thesis developed by student Jorik Van Kernenade [13], the Digital Memory Platform must fulfill all these requirements and functions to be a reliable long-term preservation service:

- Provide reliable and OAIS-compliant AIP storage facilities.
- Provide simple interfaces for the selection of archives to be retained and archived.
- Provide information on the status of archives throughout their life cycle, regardless of file format.
- Facilitate scalability of transfer speed and storage capacity if needed.
- Provide support for automation of data ingest.

- **Main components of the platform:**

- **OAIS Platform:** the backend, a web API built in Django, which orchestrates the workflows.

This platform allows users to trigger resource collection processes by creating SIPs using the BagIt Create tool or by uploading an existing SIP [2].

Another important task that must be performed by the OAIS Platform is the triggering of preservation workflows where the SIP must be sent to the designated platforms where the SIP is validated. In addition, the prepared AIPs can be sent to the new CERN Tape Archive (CTA).

It is important that all successfully harvested and ingested resources are kept in a registry, so that we can implement new tools to integrate the platform with public repositories

where to expose metadata. In fact, this last feature is what I have been working on during my internship.

- **OAIS Web:** OAIS Web is the web interface of the CERN Digital Memory platform. It gives access to most of the functions exposed by the OAIS platform API, triggers new jobs and has a complete view of all archived records, the status of their archiving process and access to their related assets (e.g., submission, archiving and dissemination packages.) [7].
- **BagIt Create:** BagIt Create is a tool to export digital repository records in packages with a consistent format, according to the CERN Submission Information Package [4] specification [1]. At the same time, the Digital Memory Platform's AIPs are based on Archivemata's AIPs [17]. (Archivemata definition available in 2.2.5)

The BagIt Create [1] tool was designed to convert records harvested from platforms in CERN's digital repositories into valid SIPs for long-term preservation, as CERN hosts several digital repositories containing relevant data produced at the institution that need to be preserved. A record usually consists of metadata and files (optionally). The BagIt Create tool extracts the necessary information from the metadata and structures the payload in the required format according to CERN AIP specifications.

- **New features:**

During my Openlab Summer Student Programme, I mainly worked on the integration of InvenioRDM with the CERN Digital Memory Platform as a public-facing repository where to consult the records archived and preserved, as well as providing the versioning system.

On my last weeks I also started to work on a pipeline for integrating a new source into the archival system to be able to preserve CERN Gitlab repositories.

2.1.3 Django

Django is a high-level, open source web framework used to build web applications. It is a web framework that provides some tools, abstracting some of the logic, and giving robustness and simplicity to help developers write efficient code.

Django is considered one of the most scalable and maintainable Python frameworks. It uses a component based on *shared-nothing* architecture, as each part of the architecture is independent of the others. In this way, any part of the code can be replaced or changed if necessary. This clear separation between the different parts leads to better scalability in case of the need to increase traffic.

In addition, Django code is written using battle-tested design principles and patterns in mind, in particular the Don't Repeat Yourself (DRY) principle or the Model View Controller (MVC) pattern. The main files of a Django project are listed below:

- **init.py:** Tells Python that the folder is a package.
- **settings.py:** Contains the configuration of the whole project.
- **urls.py:** Responsible for mapping the routes and paths in our project. For example, if you want to display something in the URL `/archives/`, you have to map it here first.
- **tasks.py:** Defines the asynchronous tasks that our platform performs in the background. Normally, in our platform these will be Celery tasks.
- **views.py:** Handles the request/response cycle for our web application.
- **models.py:** Defines the entities of our web application, the data we want to store (structure of the stored data, including field types, their maximum size, default values, etc). The models are automatically translated by Django into database tables.
- **serializers.py:** Allows you to convert complex data, such as query sets and model instances, into native Python data types that can then be easily represented in JSON, XML or other content types.

2.1.4 InvenioRDM

InvenioRDM is a turn-key research data management repository [10] powered by CERN with the aim of providing a reliable open source management repository platform to research institutions and private companies worldwide. It also seeks to create a research ecosystem to disseminate, preserve and enable reproducibility and enhance data reuse.

As for its web architecture, it has a modern web architecture and standards that facilitate its deployment, maintenance and use. InvenioRDM is being developed with a wide range of features to

streamline good data practices and drive value throughout the research lifecycle. InvenioRDM has been developed using Invenio Framework (Read more about Invenio Framework in 2.2.4).

- **Technical Specifications:**

InvenioRDM's **infrastructure architecture** is like any other typical web application. It consists of load balancers, web servers such as Apache and Nginx, application servers, a Celery distributed task queue, databases, an Elasticsearch search engine and the caching and storage system, as we can see in the following image:

Figure 3: InvenioRDM architecture [8]

In terms of **software architecture**, the InvenioRDM platform is divided into three main layers: The presentation layer, the service layer and the data layer. This modularity in the software design contributes to the segregation of responsibilities in each layer.

The presentation layer is responsible for parsing requests and directing them to the service layer. At the same time, the service layer contains most of the data control flow, including permission checking as well as semantic validation of the data. This layer can be used by many application presentation layers such as CLIs, Celery Tasks and REST APIs.

Finally, the data access layer is responsible for ensuring data integrity, data fetching and storage, and harmonization of data access for the same object across different storage systems. In this way, it can be ensured that the stored objects are persistent and stored in a reliable and performant manner [15].

• **InvenioRDM Records:**

An InvenioRDM record is a data model used to describe a primary resource of the repository: articles, datasets and code, among others.

A resource can exist in one or more versions, all of them under the same parent id, and each one with its own identifier and metadata. It is important to point out that all versions of the same resource should be accessible and editable at all times.

A record can have the following properties and characteristics:

- **Version of a record:** Each record contains its metadata for a single version of a resource.
- **Parent record:** It is an abstract entity that represents the resource in all its versions and stores all properties that are common for all record versions including the ownership, community relations and reviews. In the practical field, we have a parent record id under which we can find all the versions of the same record (different records of the same unique resource).
- **Draft:** It is a temporary version of a record, created before publication. It gathers all the related objects and save partial changes prior to being published. There are three types of drafts: **New draft**(initial draft when no record of the resource exists), **Edit draft**(a draft of an already published record version, in order to create a new version of the record) and **Next draft**(a draft without a published record version that it is not the initial draft). It is important to note that a new version of a record can be created at the same time as multiple old versions are edited.

Figure 4: Record Data models and the possible states [11]

- **Version State:** It is used to keep track of what is considered the latest version of the record and its order. However, the parent-record relationship is modeled as a tree with unordered child nodes, so there is no real order in the record versions. It is designed this way because multiple different orders may be relevant, not necessarily in a linear fashion.

Depending on the nature of the project it may make sense to sort by version number, release date or any other order.

- **InvenioRDM Requests:** A request is a method of communicating with the system or accessing system resources. However, an Invenio RDM is a functionality to support and automate requests between users or entities and the system itself. A repository usually has to deal with different types of requests such as creating a record, deleting a record, access requests, replacing a file, etc.

A request has four main properties: The creator, the receiver, the topic and the status.

- **Creator:** Is the entity that creates the request.
- **Receiver:** Is the entity that receives the request.
- **Topic:** Is the entity the request is about.
- **Status:** Represents the state a request is in in the actual moment.

The statuses a request can be in can be modelled as a state diagram. In the first moments after the request is created its state is **Created**. Then, depending if we delete the request or we submit it, it can be in two different states: **Deleted** or **Submitted**. After the request has been submitted, some actions can be performed on them and change to the following states: **Cancelled**, **Expired**, **Accepted** and **Declined**.

All this information about InvenioRDM will be of great relevance to understand the implementation, but above all, the basic concepts of versioning. This is because I have had to redefine the versioning model in InvenioRDM to be consistent with the versioning logic of the Digital Memory Platform. However, we will review these concepts throughout the document.

2.2 Definitions

2.2.1 Restful API service

It is an interface that two computer systems use to exchange information securely over the Internet. Most enterprise applications must communicate with other internal or third-party applications to perform various tasks. In our case we have to communicate the Digital Memory Platform with the InvenioRDM instance that will host our metadata.

2.2.2 REST

Representational State Transfer (REST) is a software architecture that imposes conditions on how an API should work. REST was originally created as a guideline for managing communication over a complex network such as the Internet. A REST-based architecture can be used to support reliable, high-performance communications at scale. You can easily implement and modify it, bringing cross-platform visibility and portability to any API system.

2.2.3 API

An application program interface (API) defines the rules that must be followed to communicate with other software systems. Developers expose or create APIs so that other applications can communicate with their applications programmatically.

2.2.4 Invenio Framework

Invenio Framework is an Open Source framework for large-scale digital repositories. It is JSON-native and provides RESTful APIs that allows to build apps on top of it. It is important to note that it is not by itself an end repository software, since you have to develop code [9].

2.2.5 Archivematica

Archivematica is an open-source digital preservation system in compliance with the OAIS model [17].

3 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEW FUNCTIONALITY

The new functionality developed in the CERN Digital Memory Platform, as we have discussed in previous sections, is based on the deployment of an instance of InvenioRDM as well as its integration with the platform in order to access the preserved files.

However, in order to carry out the implementation, it was done progressively, in several steps. The first one was to deploy the InvenioRDM instance following the manual provided by the InvenioRDM colleagues [12]. Then I made a base implementation to communicate the platform with the instance.

Next, the version implementation and finally the code refactoring and restructuring of the code for more scalability and modularity of the code. All these steps are described in future subchapters.

3.1 Base implementation

In my first approach to the implementation I created a fairly basic task. It created an InvenioRDM record with predefined data in a static way, without any input from the digital memory platform. In this way I managed to have the skeleton of what would be the HTTP request to be able to implement the REST API service that has to communicate the two platforms. To do so, a json schema must be defined with the appropriate format for InvenioRDM read the data to be transmitted correctly:

```
data = {
  # Variable declaration previously made
  "access": {
    "record": access,
    "files": access,
  },
  # Metadata only
  "files": {"enabled": False},
  "metadata": {
    "creators": [
      {
        "person_or_org": {
          "family_name": last_name,
          "given_name": first_name,
          "type": "personal",
        }
      }
    ],
    "publication_date": "2018/2020-09",
    "resource_type": {"id": "image-photo"},
    "title": archive.title,
  },
}
```

Listing 1: Code for the InvenioRDM data Schema

Next, the endpoint must be defined in order to create the record in InvenioRDM:

```
invenio_records_endpoint = f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}/api/records"
```

Listing 2: Code for the InvenioRDM record endpoint

Finally, to publish the file in InvenioRDM we have to make the corresponding http requests. Following Invenio's guidelines, to publish a file definitively, first we have to create the draft by means of an http request prior to the publication request. It is also very important to retrieve the data provided by the HTTP request of the draft in order to perform the identification tasks, publish the final file and manage the versions.

```
# HTTP Request to create the draft
req = requests.post(
    invenio_records_endpoint, headers=headers,
    data=json.dumps(data), verify=False
)

# Retrieve data for identification purposes and publishing the final record
data = json.loads(req.text)
id_invenio = data["id"]
relative_path = f"/records/{id_invenio}"

# Publish the InvenioRDM draft
requests.post(
    f"{invenio_records_endpoint}/{id_invenio}/draft/actions/publish",
    headers=headers,
    verify=False,
)
```

Listing 3: InvenioRDM HTTP request for draft and record publication

After these two requests, if both are successful, we have our record published in the InvenioRDM instance.

3.2 Integration with the CERN Digital Memory Platform

So far we have only published a static test record. However, our intention is that the files to be harvested on the platform will go through another stage. This stage will take place after all the preservation processes, checksum calculation and various validation processes have been applied.

Therefore, we have to integrate the code we currently have with the existing pipeline on the platform.

The first step is to create and add a new Step (Django Model) to the existing ones, such as CHECKSUM, ARCHIVE, etc. We have named the new step "INVENIO_RDM_PUSH".

```
class Steps(models.IntegerChoices):
    SIP_UPLOAD = 1
    HARVEST = 2
    VALIDATION = 3
    CHECKSUM = 4
    ARCHIVE = 5
    EDIT_MANIFEST = 6
    INVENIO_RDM_PUSH = 7
```

On the other hand, the modification of the pipeline is necessary so that the user has the option to trigger the action in case the user wishes to do so after the processes we have previously performed.

```
def get_next_steps(taskname):
    if taskname == 2 or taskname == 1:
        return [3]
    elif taskname == 3:
        return [4]
    elif taskname == 4:
        return [5,7]
    elif taskname == 7:
        return [5,7]
    elif taskname == 5:
        return [5,7]
```


We also need to generate the artifact that will be shown to the user so that he/she can access the publication created in InvenioRDM. To do this, after creating the draft, we create the artifact. And if the final publication has come out correctly it is returned as output of the function:

```
# Create a path artifact with a link to the InvenioRDM Record just created
output_invenio_artifact = {
    "artifact_name": "Invenio Link",
    "artifact_path": "test",
    "artifact_url": f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}{relative_path}",
}
...
return {"status": 0, "id": invenio_id, "artifact": output_invenio_artifact}
```

Note that to establish a connection between the Digital Memory Platform and the InvenioRDM instance we need to obtain the public-facing repository token and enter it into the platform, as specified in the repository documentation::

To be able to connect the platform with InvenioRDM, create a new API Token in your InvenioRDM instance (Log in - My Account - Applications - Personal access tokens - New token).

```
export INVENIO_API_TOKEN=<YOUR_INVENIO_API_TOKEN_HERE>
export INVENIO_SERVER_URL=<YOUR_INVENIO_SERVER_URL_HERE>
```

With what has been explained so far in the report, we can now activate the new InvenioRDM Push step and have the record exported in the public-facing repository that we have deployed.

3.3 Versioning

The functionality implemented so far allows us to publish a file in InvenioRDM. But, what happens if I make changes to the data or metadata and I want to re-archive it with the updated data? In order to manage these special cases we have to devise a version management policy that is optimal for our platform.

For our platform we have to differentiate two types of versions:

1. On a record already created, in the same pipeline.

For example, after having performed the data processing, the validation and the checksum calculation, we call the Invenio step. However, afterwards we call the Archivematica step. In this case, it is logical to want to update the metadata exposed in InvenioRDM to a new version.

2. Data has been modified outside the Digital Memory Platform.

For example, a Summer Student report is uploaded to CDS and then archived on the CERN Digital Memory Platform. However, some time later we realize that there has been a typo in the document and the relevant modification is made to the file in CDS. In this case we will have to create a new record for the modified document outside the platform. This new record, despite being different in the platform, is associated and referencing the same paper as the previous one, so they must be related in the platform as well.

The following step-by-step illustrations of the platform show how version management was solved taking into account these two cases:

1. We create a record of a document in CDS and perform all the necessary steps to create an InvenioRDM step.

Figure 5: Creation of the new InvenioRDM step

2. After executing the InvenioRDM step, the file can now be accessed in the public-facing repository. In addition, we obtain the Invenio Parent ID that will be used in the future to identify the versions we create of the file, either in the same pipeline or in a different one.

Figure 6: InvenioRDM step finished successfully with the creation of the Invenio parent ID

Figure 7: InvenioRDM artifact generated

3. Access the InvenioRDM instance through the artifact provided in the platform to see the created entry associated with the newly created file.

Figure 8: InvenioRDM artifact, first version of the archive

- Because there was an error in the file metadata, we decided to create a new version after making the necessary modifications. Therefore, we ran the InvenioRDM step again, thus generating a new artifact.

Figure 9: New InvenioRDM step to fix errors

- When we click on the generated artifact displayed on our platform we access the entry corresponding to the new version of the file in InvenioRDM. As can be seen in the illustration 10, the author has been modified. In addition, on the right side of the image we can observe the versions of the Archive. Currently we have version 1 and version 2 of the Archive 10. This archive number matches the number of the record in the CERN Digital Memory Platform.

Figure 10: New version artifact

- To illustrate the behavior of the versioning system when we create another pipeline with the same file, from the CERN Digital Memory Platform we create again a new pipeline for the same CDS file.

Figure 11: Harvest a new archive of the same resource

As shown in the image 12, before calling the InvenioRDM step we already have an associated invenio parent ID. This is because, in the implementation, when initializing a pipeline, it is checked if that file has already been previously processed. If it has, and also exists in the InvenioRDM instance, the new Record of our platform is associated with the previous record by means of the same resource (source + source id). This implementation is explained in more detail in section 3.4.

Figure 12: New record of the same resource created with same Invenio parent ID

- We run the InvenioRDM step in the new Record and access the new artifact generated in this step.

In the InvenioRDM instance we can see how a new version has been created. However, if we look at the right side of the image we can see how the name of the version does not follow the pattern followed so far. This new version of the file is a version of another archive, and therefore, it will be version 1 of archive 11.

Both Record 10 and Record 12 refer to the same file, so they are under the same invenio

Figure 13: InvenioRDM step created in the new archive

Figure 14: New artifact for the first version of the second archive

parent ID, but since they do not come from the same record, they must be differentiated in InvenioRDM to avoid confusion and to be reflected.

- 8. Finally, image 15 shows the three generated versions of the same resource under the same invenio parent ID.

Figure 15: All versions under same Invenio parent ID

3.4 Implementation of the new model

Although the basic functionality of the project was implemented, as well as version management in InvenioRDM, we had to make some significant changes. This was due to the lack of modularity, the complexity of the implemented logic and the possible future difficulty of scalability of the code. We had to refactor the code to improve the logic and make it integrate with the code already developed to date by my colleagues. Therefore, the solution we came up with was to create a new django model.

This model defines a set of attributes that all files having the same source and recid (*record id*) pair have in common. Therefore, different files that refer to the same source will refer to the same resource.

It is composed of an auto-generated unique identifier as primary key and the pair of source and id of the record in the Digital Memory Platform. In addition, it also stores the invenio parameters of the first file that creates a version (invenio id, invenio parent ID and invenio parent url). These parameters are required to create new versions due to the native implementation of InvenioRDM. The code implemented for the new Resource looks as follows:

```
class Resource(models.Model):
    id = models.AutoField(primary_key=True)

    # Source and recid (unique pair)
    source = models.CharField(max_length=50)
    recid = models.CharField(max_length=50)

    # Invenio parameters of the first archive that creates a version
    # Parameters needed for creating new versions
    invenio_id = models.CharField(max_length=50)
    invenio_parent_id = models.CharField(
        max_length=150, default=None, blank=True, null=True
    )
    invenio_parent_url = models.CharField(
        max_length=150, default=None, blank=True, null=True
    )
```



```

# Set invenio_id of the first archive that pushes a version to InvenioRDM
def set_invenio_id(self, invenio_id):
    self.invenio_id = invenio_id
    self.save()

# Set the values for both fields that need the invenio_parent_id
def set_invenio_parent_fields(self, invenio_parent_id):
    self.invenio_parent_id = invenio_parent_id
    self.invenio_parent_url = f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}/search?q=
        parent.id:{invenio_parent_id}&f=allversions:true"
    self.save()

```

Listing 4: Code for the implementation of the new Resource model [5].

On the other hand, all the step flow logic was restructured into a method that is executed by a Celery task in the background. This method publish an Archive on our platform as a new Record on the configured InvenioRDM instance. If the Archive was already published, create a new version of the Record. If another Archive referring to the same (Source, Record ID) was already published, create a new version of the Record.

```

@shared_task(
    name="processInvenio", bind=True, ignore_result=True, after_return=finalize
)
def invenio(self, archive_id, step_id, input_data=None):

    logger.info(f"Starting the publishing to InvenioRDM of Archive {archive_id}")

    # Get the Archive and Step we're running for
    archive = Archive.objects.get(pk=archive_id)
    step = Step.objects.get(pk=step_id)
    step.set_status(Status.IN_PROGRESS)

    # The InvenioRDM API endpoint
    invenio_records_endpoint = f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}/api/records"

```



```
# Set up the authentication for the requests to the InvenioRDM API
headers = {
    "Authorization": "Bearer " + INVENIO_API_TOKEN,
    "Content-type": "application/json",
}

# If this Archive was never published before to InvenioRDM
# and no similar Archive was published before
if (archive.resource.invenio_parent_id) is None:

    # We create a brand new Record in InvenioRDM
    archive.invenio_version = 1
    data = initialize_data(archive)

    try:
        # Create a record as a InvenioRDM draft
        req = requests.post(
            invenio_records_endpoint,
            headers=headers,
            data=json.dumps(data),
            verify=False,
        )
        req.raise_for_status()
    except requests.exceptions.HTTPError as err:
        print(f"The request didn't succeed:{err}")
        step.set_status(Status.FAILED)
        return {"status": 1, "ERROR": err}

# Parse the response and get our new record ID so we can link it
data_loaded = json.loads(req.text)
invenio_id = data_loaded["id"]
relative_path = f"/records/{invenio_id}"
```



```

# Create a path artifact with a link to the InvenioRDM Record we just created
output_invenio_artifact = {
    "artifact_name": "Invenio Link",
    "artifact_path": "test",
    "artifact_url": f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}{relative_path}",
}

# Publish the InvenioRDM draft so it's accessible publicly
req_publish_invenio = requests.post(
    f"{invenio_records_endpoint}/{invenio_id}/draft/actions/publish",
    headers=headers,
    verify=False,
)

# An InvenioRDM parent ID groups every version of the same Record, extract it
data_published = json.loads(req_publish_invenio.text)
invenio_parent_id = data_published["parent"]["id"]
# Set the value to the resource fields for the first time
resource = archive.resource
resource.set_invenio_id(invenio_id)
resource.set_invenio_parent_fields(invenio_parent_id)
# Save the resource and the archive
resource.save()
archive.save()

# Create a new InvenioRDM version of an already published Record
else:
    # Invenio_id of the first version published in InvenioRDM of the resource
    invenio_id = archive.resource.invenio_id
    # Create new version as draft
    req_invenio_draft_new_version = requests.post(
        f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}/api/records/{invenio_id}/versions",
        headers=headers,
        verify=False,
    )
    # Get the ID of the draft we just created

```



```

new_version_invenio_id = json.loads(req_invenio_draft_new_version.text)["id"]

# Increment the version
archive.invenio_version += 1

# Initialize the archive data that is going to be sent on the request
new_version_data = initialize_data(archive)

# Update draft with the new adata
requests.put(
    f"{invenio_endpoint}/{new_version_invenio_id}/draft",
    headers=headers,
    data=json.dumps(new_version_data),
    verify=False,
)

# Publish the new Invenio RDM version draft
requests.post(
    f"{invenio_endpoint}/{new_version_invenio_id}/draft/actions/publish",
    headers=headers,
    verify=False,
)

archive.save()

# Create a InvenioRDM path artifact with a link to the new version
relative_path = f"/records/{new_version_invenio_id}"
output_invenio_artifact = {
    "artifact_name": "Invenio Link",
    "artifact_path": "test",
    "artifact_url": f"{INVENIO_SERVER_URL}{relative_path}",
}

return {"status": 0, "id": invenio_id, "artifact": output_invenio_artifact}

```

Listing 5: InvenioRDM publication logic implementation code

4 ADDITIONAL WORK DEVELOPED IN THE DIGITAL MEMORY PLATFORM

During my stay at CERN, in addition to developing the main functionality of the InvenioRDM integration with the CERN Memory Platform, I also performed other tasks on the platform. I made the necessary changes in the frontend to be able to translate everything done in the backend so that the user could make use of the functionality.

In addition, I solved some Gitlab issues in the platform that we discovered while we were testing and developing the platform, which is already in production.

5 FUTURE WORK

Since the platform is still under development, there is still work to be done on it.

The integration of new pipelines as a source of information to be archived is one of the jobs to be done in the future, with Gitlab being one of the most crucial sources to be integrated.

On the other hand, other colleagues are working on local uploading of files in order to preserve local data that CERN users have on their local computers, without having the need to upload them to one of the source-enabled platforms of the CERN Digital Memory Platform.

Another area where work still needs to be done is the proposed approach to managing multiple versions. It is currently a baseline approach that needs to be refined and integrated with other parts of the platform to be consistent across the platform and with all file upload options.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

During my nine weeks at CERN I have honed and learned a wide variety of technologies, frameworks and platforms that I did not have as much knowledge of before this experience.

In the research and technology realm, data preservation is not talked about as much as it is with security, artificial intelligence or machine learning. However, data preservation is a challenging and critical area in computer science.

I would also like to thank my supervisors and section colleagues for guiding and teaching me throughout my stay, as well as making me feel part of the team. I really could not have been in a better team.

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